

Classical Energy Distributions in Terms of Phase Space

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Emphasis seems to be placed on spatial arrangements when developing the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution and on arrangements over “energy degenerate” cells (i.e. phase space) with a fixed single particle energy e_i in quantum mechanics. In the MB case, particles are independent, while in the quantum case, single particle energy levels are independent, immediately “forcing” a grand canonical approach in which the total number of particles is not conserved.

In this note, we try to argue that the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution follows directly from the quantum phase space approach in the case that $n(e_i)$ is very small compared with the degeneracy (cells) in phase space i.e. $d^3p dV / h^3$.

Maxwell-Boltzmann Microcanonical Approach

In a previous note, we presented an expression for the number of “spatial” arrangements of particles in the MB approach. To do this, we divided energy into tiny pieces E/a (a is a large number) and considered V inner partitions. Then:

$$\text{Microcanonical number of spatial arrangements} = (E/a + V)! / [(E/a)! V!] \quad ((1))$$

In many macrostate terms in ((1)), there are no particles representing various single particle energies e_i . It has been shown in a previous note that for small e , removing this e from ((1)) and calculating the probability yields $\exp(-e_i/X)$ or the Maxwell-Boltzmann form. ((1)) shows particles are not independent because if e is of the order of E , there is a strong effect on the energy of the remaining particles. It may be noted ((1)) counts “some kind” of position i.e. a particle with $3E/a$ followed by one with $5E/a$ is counted separately from one with $5E/a$ followed by $3E/a$. This is usually interpreted as describing spatial arrangements, but this may not be the only interpretation. For example, if one takes $V=N$, the number of particles, for low e , one finds that $P(e)=C \exp(-e/ (E/N))$, but E/N is not temperature. As a result, it may be more convenient to think of ((1)) as representing arrangements of e_i values of a single independent particle in time, with V being related to time slices. One may fix X in $\exp(-e/X)$ by requiring that:

$$\text{Integral density}(e) de \exp(-e/X) = E/N \quad ((2))$$

It is interesting that ((1)) is usually mapped into a maximization problem (1) with:

$$N! / [\text{Product over } i \text{ } n_i!] \quad \text{subject to} \quad \text{Sum over } i \text{ } n_i = 1 \quad \text{Sum over } i \text{ } e_i n_i = E \quad ((3))$$

Here n_i is the number of particles with energy e_i . The constraints are added using Lagrange multipliers. One may note that n_i may be less than 1 and that it may also be fractional. Thus, the equilibrium set of e_i does not necessarily coincide with a physical set of n_i . Furthermore,

allowing n_i to be very small, allows $e_i > E_{\text{total}}$ which is also unphysical. Thus, it seems one is introducing a canonical approach in a somewhat “ambiguous” manner as these limitations are usually not pointed out. ((3)) allows for complete independence of particles and is often interpreted as describing positions in space (1). It could equally well describe energy e_i values in time. One may see that ((3)) is only an approximation of ((1)), the microcanonical approach, especially since it only focuses on the set of n_i which maximize ((3)). This may be related to average two body reaction balance $f(e_i)f(e_j)=f(e_k)f(e_l)$ and $e_i+e_j=e_k+e_l$ which also yields $f(e_i)=C \exp(-e_i/T)$. The $f(e_i)$ calculated by using ((1)) and averaging over all possible physical arrangements is not $\exp(-e_i/T)$ for all cases it seems. Only for $e_i < T$ does the MB apply. Thus, for the microcanonical scheme, one argues that every macrostate has a weight of 1, but then a calculation such as ((3)) only pick out a “fictitious” set of n_i which have a maximum number of arrangements in space or time.

In previous notes, we argued that one may obtain the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution through the consideration of average reaction balance. For example, one considers the probability for an $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$ reaction to occur (with specific momenta alignments). Then, this is equated with the probability of the time reversed reaction. For example, $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$. Taking \ln of both sides and linking to energy conservation during the reaction yields the MB distribution. We argue that two body reactions are the physical driver of equilibrium in an MB gas. The above energy arrangements using factorials should mirror the physics of the reactions. In other words, one does not make energy distribution arguments a priori because they may conflict with constraints which exist for two body reactions. For the MB case, one only has the elastic (energy conservation) constraint, but one might “imagine” a system in which the probability for e_1 to react is not proportional to $f(e_1)$. In such a case, the energy distribution would be driven by the reaction rules and not only on the partitioning of energy, it seems.

Quantum Mechanical Approach and Its Link to the Maxwell-Boltzmann Distribution

In quantum statistical mechanics (bosons and fermions), it seems the focus is on single particle state occupation. Degeneracy is introduced $g(e_i)$ for each e_i and particles are arranged among the degenerate cells for each e_i . Thus, a maximization approach is again introduced, but one of a different nature from that of the MB case i.e. in (1) one maximizes:

$$\ln\left\{ \text{Product over } i \frac{g_i (N_i+g_i-1)!}{[N_i! g_i!]} \right\} \text{ subject to } \sum \text{ over } i N_i = N \text{ and } \sum \text{ over } i e_i N_i = E \quad ((4))$$

Here g_i is the degeneracy. It is very important, but exists in both the classical and quantum pictures. One does not need to completely separate the quantum picture from the classical, it seems as is usually done. In the classical situation, every (p_x, p_y, p_z) point represents a particle, but not in the quantum case, where $\Delta p_i \Delta x \approx h$. Thus, $g_i = \int d^3p \, dV / h^3$. g_i , the degeneracy, may be small or large. In the classical case, it is very large. Thus, for the quantum case to approach the classical, g_i should be large, and for the quantum (boson) case, g_i should be small. In other words, the maximization of ((4)) subject to constraints should hold for both the quantum and classical (Maxwell-Boltzmann) cases, but one usually only sees it applied to the

quantum case. Later, once the Bose Einstein distribution is obtained it is often shown that under certain limits, it becomes the MB. Those limits should exist already at the level of ((4)), we argue.

Consider first the general maximization of ((4)) with N_i large, subject to constraints. One obtains, as shown in texts, the Bose Einstein distribution: $f(e_i) = g_i / [\exp((e_i - u)/T) - 1]$ if one uses Stirling's approximation: $\ln(n!) \approx n \ln(n)$.

Next, consider g_i very small, say 2 for the sake of argument. Then ((4)) collapses to:

$(n_i + 1)! / n_i! = n_i + 1$ No Stirling approximation is needed. One maximizes:

$\ln(n_i + 1) + b_1 n_i + b_2 e_i n_i$ to obtain $1/(n_i + 1) = -b_1 - b_2 e_i$

Consider cases of n_i being large. Then $-b_1 - b_2 e_i = (e_i - u)/T$ should be very small. Add 1 to both sides: $1 + 1/(n_i + 1) = 1 + (e_i - u)/T = \exp((e_i - u)/T)$ or $n_i + 1 \approx n_i = 1 / [\exp((e_i - u)/T) - 1]$.

Thus, large n_i and small g_i are associated with the quantum boson case.

(It seems the approach of focusing on the occupation of single particle states, and treating these as independent leads to fluctuating numbers of particles. Thus, the constraint $\sum_i N_i = N$ is a kind of average with total particle numbers differing from N . This is not at first apparent from the way in which ((4)) is formulated. In addition, N_i may be less than 1 (i.e. very small) leading to $e_i > N_i$ still satisfying $\sum_i e_i N_i = E$. Thus, the grand canonical scheme is used, although this is not often explicitly stated.)

Link Between Quantum and Classical Distributions

As a next step, consider ((4)) with g_i very large i.e. $g_i \gg n_i$. We argue this is the Maxwell-Boltzmann scenario and that ((4)) may be used to develop the MB distribution even without considering quantum considerations. Then:

$\ln[(n_i + g_i)! / (g_i! n_i!)] \approx (n_i + g_i) \ln(g_i + n_i) - g_i \ln(g_i) - n_i \ln(n_i) = n_i \ln(g_i) + n_i + n_i^2/n_i/g - n_i \ln(n_i)$

Approx = $-n_i \ln(n_i) + n_i \ln(g_i)$ if Stirling's approximation is used.

The term $n_i \ln(g_i)$ becomes $\ln(g_i)$ under the variation of n_i and then taking exp yields g_i or the phase space volume.

$N_i \ln(n_i)$, however, is the usual term which appears in $N! / \text{Product over } i n_i!$ Thus, ((4)) with $g_i \gg n_i$, i.e. considering maximizing arrangements in phase space $d^3p dV / h^3$ yields the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution. Thus, one does not necessarily need to think of spatial arrangements (or even time arrangements).

Link with Average Reaction Balance

We argued above that the MB distribution may be obtained using average reaction balance $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ together with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. How does this link to the maximization of arrangements of N_i particles (associated with e_i) in a volume of phase space? We argue that for $f(e_1)$ to be proportional to the probability for a particle with e_1 to react with e_2 , one does not want to have any preferred momentum direction incorporated in $f(e_1)$. In order to have an elastic collision, say $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$, only a certain momenta or series of momenta orientation sets may work. One may find a p_1 vector corresponding to e_1 and then assign p_2, p_3, p_4 such that both momentum and energy is conserved. In terms of p_1 , one may rotate the picture, so that other p_1 directions are possible. Thus, one does not want any preferred direction in phase space. We argue it is actually the reaction which allows one to maximize the uncertainty of occupation in phase space, which is the main point, it seems, behind a phase space derivation of the MB distribution which is also directly related to a quantum approach.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that one does not need two factorial schemes, one for the classical Maxwell-Boltzmann case and the other for the quantum (especially Bose Einstein) case. (For example, separate schemes are used in both (1) and (2).) The factorial scheme of ((4)) represents both the quantum result, holding for g_i =degeneracy being low compared to n_i , and the classical case with $g_i \gg n_i$. Thus, the Maxwell-Boltzmann distribution may be obtained by considering the maximization of arrangements in phase space. We argue this corresponds to the reaction balance $f(e_1)f(e_2)=f(e_3)f(e_4)$ together with $e_1+e_2=e_3+e_4$. In fact, we argue that reaction balance drives the various arrangement schemes used.

References

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